

Omentin prevents venous neointimal hyperplasia in arteriovenous fistula by suppressing inflammation and inhibiting hypoxia inducible factor-1 α expression

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Supplementary table 1. The following primers were used:

Gene	Sequence
HIF-1 α	Forward: 5'-TGCTTGGTGCTGATTTGTGA-3' Reverse: 5'-GGTCAGATGATCAGAGTCCA-3'
VEGF	Forward: 5'-CGAGACCTTGGTGGACATC-3' Reverse: 5'-CTGCATGGTGACGTTGAAC-3'
MMP-2	Forward: 5'-AGCCTTCTCACCCCCACCTG-3', Reverse: 5'-GCCCTTATCCCACTGCCCC-3'
MMP-9	Forward: 5'-AACACACACGACGTCTTCCA-3' Reverse: 5'-TGCAGGATGTCAAAGCTCAC-3'
IL-6	Forward: 5'-CTTCCAGCCAGTTGCCTTCT-3' Reverse: 5'-GAGAGCATTGGAAGTTGGG-3'
MCP-1	Forward: 5'-AGCCAGACGCAGTGAATTC-3' Reverse: 5'-TCACGGAGATGGTCTTGTTG-3'
TNF- α	Forward: 5'-CCAGTTCTCTTCAGCGGTCAAGGC-3' Reverse: 5'-ACTCGGCAAGGTCCAGGTAAGG-3'

Supplementary Figure

Supplementary Figure S1. Creation of carotid-jugular arteriovenous fistula (AVF) and changes in serum urea and creatinine concentrations in rabbits after nephrectomy. (a) The left common jugular vein (LCJV) was used for a side-to-side anastomosis to the left common carotid artery (LCCA). **(b)** The serum urea and creatinine levels were significantly increased at the second week after nephrectomy and increased continually during the experiment until they were ~3-fold greater than the normal range at the fourth week, after which they stabilized. * $P < 0.05$.

Supplementary Figure S2. Omentin inhibited HIF-1 α expression at the protein level and downregulated expression of downstream VEGF and MMP-2/9 at the gene and protein levels. (a, b, c and d). The protein levels of HIF-1 α and MMP-2/9 in control animals and animal models treated with or without omentin were evaluated by western blot analysis. Representative blots showing HIF-1 α and MMP-2/9 are shown in panel a. The relative levels of these protein normalized to the levels of GAPDH are shown in panels b, c and d. (e) The VEGF levels in the sera of control animals and model animals treated with or without omentin were evaluated by ELISA. (f, g, h and i) The mRNA expression of HIF-1 α , VEGF and MMP2/9 in pVSMCs isolated from control animals and model animals treated with or without omentin. The mRNA levels of HIF-1 α , VEGF and MMP2/9 were measured by quantitative real-time PCR. There

was no significant difference in the mRNA levels of HIF-1 α among the three groups.

All results were normalized to GAPDH. The data are presented as the mean \pm S.D.. *

$p < 0.05$.